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THE ROLE OF A WOMAN VOTING IN THE 1919 LEGISLATIVE SEJM ELECTIONS

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This article presents the subject of the role of women voting in elections to the Legislative Sejm. However, this is not the story of women recognized by society and elected representatives in the Sejm of the reborn Poland. This is the story of women who were called for the first time to vote in elections. Receiving full public rights after many years of ignorance on the part of men, they were urged and encouraged to appear in elections. The main inspiration for this article was to find leaflets, posters and appeals to Polish citizens before the elections to the 1919 legislative parliament. We were impressed by the number of appeals to women who began to be treated as full citizens of the Second Polish Republic. After reviewing the materials, we decided to familiarize the reader with the reality of the parliamentary elections and the role of women they played in this important event of rebuilding Poland.

Key words: women, electoral law; legislative Sejm; voting; elections; Second Polish Republic; Polish Socialist Party; National Independence Party.

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Роль жіночих голосів у виборах до законодавчого Сейму у 1919 році

У цій статті представлена тема ролі жінок, які голосують на виборах до законодавчого сейму. Однак це не історія жінок, визнаних суспільством та обраних представницями у Сеймі відродженої Польщі. Це історія жінок, яких

вперше було закликано голосувати на виборах. Отримавши повні публічні права після багаторічного невизнання з боку чоловіків, їх закликали і заохочували брати участь у виборах. Основним натхненням для цієї статті було знайти листівки, плакати та звернення до громадян Польщі перед виборами до законодавчого парламенту 1919 року. Нас вразила кількість звернень до жінок, до яких почали ставитися як до повноправних громадян Другої Польської Республіки. Переглянувши матеріали, ми вирішили ознайомити читача з реальністю парламентських виборів та роллю жінок, яку вони відіграли у цій важливій події відбудови Польщі.

Ключові слова: жінки; виборче законодавство; законодавчий сейм; голосування; вибори; Друга Польська Республіка; Польська Соціалістична Партія; Партія Національної Незалежності.

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Роль женских голосов в выборах в законодательный Сейм в 1919 году

В этой статье представлена тема роли женщин, которые голосуют на выборах в законодательный сейм. Однако это не история женщин, признанных обществом и избранных представительницами в Сейме возрожденной Польши. Это история женщин, которые впервые призвали голосовать на выборах. Получив полные публичные права после многолетнего непризнания со стороны мужчин, их призывали и поощряли участвовать в выборах. Основным вдохновением для этой статьи было найти листовки, плакаты и обращения к гражданам Польши перед выборами в законодательный парламент 1919 года. Нас поразило количество обращений к женщинам, к которым стали относиться как к полноправным гражданам Второй Польской Республики. Просмотрев материалы, мы решили ознакомить читателя с реальностью парламентских выборов и ролью женщин, которые сыграли роль в этом важном событии восстановления Польши.

Ключевые слова: женщины; избирательное законодательство; законодательный сейм; голосования, выборы; Вторая Польская Республика; Польская Социалистическая партия; Партия Национальной Независимости.

Introduction

This article presents the role of women in elections to the Legislative Sejm in 1919. However, this is not the story of women recognized by society and elected

deputies of the reviving Polish state. This is the story of women who were called for the first time to vote in elections. Receiving full public rights after many years of ignorance on the part of men, they were urged and encouraged to appear in elections. The main inspiration for this article was to find leaflets, posters and appeals to Polish citizens on the eve of elections to the 1919 legislative parliament.

The analysis of sources and recent researches

These materials were collected by the Potocki and Ostrowski families in their archives. All leaflets, appeals, brochures and notes were collected by the family on their own, which was associated with a strong connection of the Potocki and Ostrowski lives with politics. In addition to the men actively participating in it, the Potocki and Ostrowski families included female representatives showing interest in politics – this is mainly about Ludwika the Countess of Ostrowska. As many as 20 brochures, leaflets, posters and notes in the materials from the Potocki and Ostrowski Archives in Maluszyn refer to women. This shows considerable interest in the female issue of archive owners. Due to the fact that one of the authors of this article in the past has dealt with the Potocki and Ostrowski families, among others in the works of Ludwika Countess Ostrowska (Studnicka-Mariańczyk, 2016) or the Manor House of Korowski Family in Maluszyn (Studnicka-Mariańczyk, 2014), she drew attention to the materials characterizing the times and reality in which the Potocki family lived and Ostrowski. The reality and political situation are shown in leaflets and appeals from various political parties to citizens. In addition to strong agitation, one can deduce from them what in the political life of that time was a priority for society – including women. Due to the high historical value of the materials found and the surprisingly large number of appeals to women as full citizens of the Second Polish Republic, the authors decided to address the issue of women's first voting in Poland. The analysis of found source materials evoked in the authors a sense of duty to bring the reader closer to the reality of the parliamentary elections and the role of women they played in this important event for rebuilding Poland.

Currently, there are monographs in the literature describing the elections to the Legislative Sejm and its activities in subsequent years, as well as the role of women related to this issue. One of them is the work of Jerzy Myśliński – *Women in inter-war Poland* (Myśliński, 2000), who accurately described the main lines of action of socialists. A significant position is also the work of Maria Nartonowicz-Kot, *A socialist in the political and social life of Poland in the interwar years* (Nartonowicz-Kot, 1966). The exact characteristics of the Polish Socialist Party are included in their works by Jan Tomicki – *Polish Socialist Party* (Tomicki, 1983) and Kazimierz Więch *Polish Socialist Party 1918–1921* (Więch, 1978). Regarding the second part of this article – the analysis of the appeal of the Women's Independence Party – Grzegorz Zackiewicz's article entitled *Vision of independent Poland in the concepts of the National Independence Party from 1917–1919* (Zackiewicz, 2018).

Presenting the research material

The newly created state, which was the Second Polish Republic, after over a hundred years of captivity, had to rebuild all administrative, legislative and governmental structures. After regaining independence, the Poles vigorously set about laying foundations for a strong and free state. On November 18, 1918, Józef Piłsudski, who had received command of the Polish Armed Forces from the Regency Council a few days earlier, established the first Government of the Second Polish Republic (Lange, 1919). A few days later, he issued a statement to other countries of the world about the emergence of independent Poland (Chronicle..., 1994). Jędrzej Moraczewski became the President of the Council of Ministers (Lange, 1919, p. 43). Then a decree was signed, signed by Marshal Piłsudski and Prime Minister Moraczewski, regarding the establishment of Polish representative power until the convocation of the legislative parliament. Piłsudski's competence included appointing the government and senior state officials as well as approving decrees issued by the government (Czubiński, 1987). The main purpose of the government formed by Piłsudski was to organize elections to the legislative parliament. At the end of November 1918, the rules for electoral regulations were issued, and the date of the elections was specified – January 26, 1919 (Lange, 1919, p. 43). It was one of the most important elements of the reconstruction of the state. The elections were to be five adjectives: equal – every citizen had the right to take part in the elections and had one vote; direct – each citizen voted for one candidate from electoral lists; secret; proportional – political groups received the number of seats in proportion to the votes received; universal – all adult citizens of the Second Polish Republic could vote (Decree, 1919, p. 2). All citizens who were 21 years of age had electoral rights. Other factors, such as religion, nationality, social origin or gender, which until now had a significant impact on the selection of people entitled to vote did not matter anymore (Rzepecki, 1920, pp. 9–19).

The novelty was allowing women to vote. Polish citizens received this right for the first time in their history. Therefore, it was an event that strongly influenced the environment of women activists (Sierakowska, 2009, pp. 33–47). They then achieved their primary goal in equality with men (Pietrzak, 2000, pp. 77–91). They became full citizens of the country in which they lived and worked. It should be noted that in the then world the right to vote for women was not customary in other European countries. In the reviving Republic of Poland, the authorities were one of the first in Europe that decided to grant women such rights. Obtaining electoral rights by women was used by political and social activists who wanted to take full advantage of the opportunity to represent women's thought in the group of legislative authorities (Śliwa, 2000, pp. 49–60). It is worth emphasizing that the merit of obtaining women's electoral rights should be attributed to them. It was a complex process, which was successful, and it included the work of many activists (Waniek, 2019). The requirement to be on the electoral list was to obtain 50 signatures supporting the

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candidacy (Czubiński, 1987, pp. 48–49). In the absence of support for Jędrzej Moraczewski, he resigned along with the government on January 16, 1919 (Goclon, 2009, p. 135). Then his place was taken by Ignacy Paderewski, who formed a new government. The issue of elections to the Legislative Sejm was quite complicated in the reviving Polish State. These problems resulted mainly from the division of Polish territories, which were not finally unified yet. In January 1919, citizens from parts of the Kingdom of Poland voted. In February 1919, citizens of the Second Polish Republic from Suwalszczyzna voted, in June from Greater Poland and in July from Białystok.

Election to the Legislative Sejm was attended by: The National Election Committee of Democratic Parties, the Polish People's Party "Liberation", the Polish Socialist Party, the Polish People's Union, the Provisional Jewish National Council, the Polish People's Party "Piast", the National Workers' Union and others. Then the largest number of votes was won by the National Electoral Committee of Democratic Parties (Kacperski, 2007, p. 115), which included the National Democratic Party, the Christian Democratic Party, the Polish Progressive Party, the National Union, and the National Electoral Action of Polish Women. After a few weeks, the Real Political Party, the National Rebirth Party, the National Labor Party, the Political Circle of Workers' Associations, the Christian Workers' Association and the Economic Independence Union joined the original composition (Drewicz, 2012, pp. 86–87). The Polish Liberation Party took the second place during the January election. PSL From the beginning of its existence, it supported the activities of the Polish Military Organization and the Ambulance League of Women. The Polish Socialist Party took the third place in the election (Czubiński, 1987, p. 54).

Currently, before the election, citizens often face election campaigns, just as it was 100 years ago. After the agreed date of elections to the Legislative Sejm, the parties agitated among Polish citizens in their favor. Among the numerous appeals, posters, leaflets and programs of leading political parties, whose authors were men, women also began to speak. One such initiative was the appeal of the Women's Department of the Polish Socialist Party (The Central Archives of Historical Records, the Ostrowski and Potocki Archives of Maluszyn, Prints of elections..., 1919) issued in 1919 (The establishment of the women's department of the Polish Socialist Party dates back to December 8–9, 1918, when the first Party Congress of Women took place – see Waniek, 2019). Already at the beginning of the appeal of the PPS activists, it was emphasized how important the elections to the Legislative Sejm would be, which in the near future will adopt the constitution of the Second Polish Republic – a basic law organizing the rights, obligations and system of the newly reborn state. The importance of choosing the right people to decide about further shaping the state was also emphasized. As the appeal came from the Women's Department of the PPS, it emphasized the paramount importance of choosing representatives of the working people, which – according to the activists – constituted the majority of Polish society.

As mentioned above, the appeal states that women have obtained voting rights on an equal footing with men. However, it was shown not only as a right, but also as a civic duty. PPS activists defined the program of the PPS Women's Department as follows:

"(...) it combined the slogans of socialism and feminism, in which the statement of dual – class and gender – handicap of workers played an important role. The activities of socialists were not limited to the struggle for economic liberation of women, protection of their work, building women's trade unions. An equally important task was to work to make the female proletariat aware of what equality is (Waniek, 2019).

According to the authors of the magazine, women should consider the right to vote as an obligation to make up for the current inability to cast a vote, which pushed them to the margins of political life. They also believed that the vote should take place after deep reflection and only on representatives of socialism, under the threat of suffering defeat as a citizen in the event that:

"they will cast their voices to those who have always thrown them away from the brace of public life, saying that the woman is to remain silent in matters of politics, deaf to their misery, when they cast their votes to the backslides, the enemies of working people, the enemies of all liberation movement!" (The Central Archives of Historical Records, the Ostrowski and Potocki Archives of Maluszyn, Prints of elections..., 1919, p. 3).

The authors of appeals addressed to women of the reviving Polish state threatened the assessment of future generations and criticism of them – as citizens making bad choices, the effects of which will be felt by future generations. In our opinion, the authors of the appeal try to reach all women from different social strata and with different social and political views. The next part of the document makes women aware of the need to speak and fight for this voice with ubiquitous men. Following the appeal:

"Many of them consider politics at all to belong to them, political matters say only care about men" (The Central Archives of Historical Records, the Ostrowski and Potocki Archives of Maluszyn, Prints of elections..., 1919, p. 4).

This illustrates the division that existed between the women's community in the 20th century. Despite the individualities who wanted to act and have a voice as a full citizen of the country, the remaining – a large proportion of women did not want to interfere in politics, considering it not interesting and not worthy of deeper interest (Kulak, 2016, pp. 24–25). This is completely justified, and this is because of the past, in which the role of a woman was reduced to taking care of the home, giving birth and raising children, and in later centuries also work (Kasprzyk, 2017). Women were taught about their position in marriage, about the domination of personal and public life by a man. Therefore, women who did not want to engage in political life were

somewhat justified by the history and role of the woman she played in society. Of course, this does not mean that women still remained “subjected” to their husband and, in general, the male world in public space, because more and more of them were educated, so that they were aware of the situation in the country, and obtaining political rights was significant for them social promotion, which made it possible to decide about the current situation in the country. Returning to the appeal of the PPS activists, in the remainder of the appeal they listed matters that should be of interest to every citizen, such as: borders of the Polish state, taxes that will be adopted in the future, relations with neighbors, resolutions on the rights of employees, etc. Pay attention to the fact that all these matters significantly affect the lives of not only men, but also working women or women – mothers. The activists firmly disagree with the women community's obligation to vote. The authors drew attention to another aspect of allowing women to fully enjoy public rights – namely the possibility of co-deciding on aspects related to women's lives. Until now, men often decided about women's matters without putting themselves in their place. Henceforth, after getting into the Legislative Sejm female representatives, they could be the voice of women in political discussions and matters concerning them. The activists also indicated the need to get involved in a political organization, because in their opinion they only had the chance to fight the overwhelming number of men involved in politics forever. The PPS was shown as a political organization that will fight to defend the oppressed women. The appeal also deplores the authors on working women who have not yet had any impact on labor legislation. Numbers listed:

“(…) before the war, 6 million women in Austria worked for money, while in Germany 12 million” (The Central Archives of Historical Records, the Ostrowski and Potocki Archives of Maluszyn, Prints of elections..., 1919, p. 5).

The authors also pointed out that during the war it was women who worked the most, taking over the positions of men who were directed to the front. In addition, it should be noted that in an appeal to women, PPS activists spoke loudly about widespread hunger wages for women who, after the war, despite the work they had to do, often faced the disability of her husband who returned home. The authors also pointed to the lack of social assistance for women:

“In greater numbers doomed to their own work and transition, without anyone's help hard way of life, are women in this situation that in the event of illness or childbirth, in the event of unemployment and old age they must suffer misery and are abused at every step” (The Central Archives of Historical Records, the Ostrowski and Potocki Archives of Maluszyn, Prints of elections..., 1919, p. 6).

The authors of the text also argued about the protection that the Polish Socialist Party has in the past provided for working women. They pointed out the mortality of women working mainly in tobacco, phosphorus and lead factories. The authors enumerated numerous hardships of war and post-war life. Expensive in shops,

the need for women who, after work, had to take care of the entire farm and children. They also indicated the amount of taxes that had an impact on the life of the entire nation. In their appeal calling for votes at the elections to the Legislative Sejm, the activists presented postulates concerning the life of a pregnant woman and the mother of an infant, which should be changed with the establishment of a new parliament. Woman:

“1) should be dismissed from work with the right to return to her – 8 weeks before delivery and 8 weeks after delivery; all this time she should receive a allowance no lower than 1^{1/2} of her earnings.

2) should benefit from free midwifery and medical assistance; have free help provided at the farm and taking care of children from special substitutes during the puerperium. In cases of need mothers should receive underwear, children's layettes and all that is necessary for raising a baby in cleanliness and health.

3) nursing women who have returned to work should be released every few hours to feed their child. They should receive an additional payment equal to half of their earnings. There should be cribs for infants not far from the worker's mother's workplace, which would allow her to feed the child without taking a long break from the work.

4) all these allowances should be issued from state funds through special maternity funds” (The Central Archives of Historical Records, the Ostrowski and Potocki Archives of Maluszyn, Prints of elections..., 1919, p. 11).

Then PPS activists drew attention to the decisive influence of women on education in the country. They also stated that obtaining a political voice by women is in the interest of the entire nation, which would develop much better.

In their summary, they highlighted the primary importance of the matters they cited to readers. They considered it necessary for women to be involved in political and public life of the state in order to have an impact on all matters related to women's life. The activists drew attention to the possibility of women's representation by a woman who could raise issues important to the women's community, often overlooked by men. At the end of their appeal, they called for voting for the Polish Socialist Party as the duty of a good citizen who cares about the fate and future of her country:

“Women Citizens! Mostly in the nation, you can tip the scales of victory to the side of those fighting for a good cause, so let them not shirk their vote and fulfill their duty in the name of the highest goal that we strive for in the name of future generations! – Women's Department of the Polish Socialist Party” (The Central Archives of Historical Records, the Ostrowski and Potocki Archives of Maluszyn, Prints of elections..., 1919, p. 16).

Other political parties also wanted to use their influence on women who obtained the right to vote in the next vote. In addition to the appeal of the activists of

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the Polish Socialist Party described above, the National Independence Party expressed its opinion addressed to the women's community (The National Independence Party – founded in March 1917, a group of the left wing of independence, cooperated with the Polish Military Organization. Its ranks mainly included urban intelligence. The main activists of the Party were: Jan Cynarski, Bolesław Czarkowski, Gustaw Daniłowski, Medard Downarowicz, Piotr Górecki, Tadeusz Hołówko, Waław Sieroszewski, Artur Śliwiński, and Stanisław Thugutt. G. Zackiewicz, cit. pp. 189–210). In a brochure entitled *A Woman's Task in the Legislative Sejm*, the authors tried to win the votes of women. From the very beginning, activists in the brochure emphasize the importance of the upcoming elections, treating them as decisive for the overall revival of the Polish state. The authors expressed their approval for the electoral law, believing that the principles on which the elections are to be conducted are completely democratic and correct. In addition, they compared the democratic electoral code to the code of other countries in the world – according to the authors in the most democratic nations:

“This broad democratic electoral law, which is used in the most cultural and democratic nations (Scandinavian, Finnish, US, Australia, and recently England) opens up new horizons for Polish women for political and civic work and gives her the right to feel state-creative cooperation” (The Central Archives of Historical Records, the Ostrowski and Potocki Archives of Maluszyn..., 1919, Party of National Independence, p. 1)

And in this appeal, as well as in the appeal of the PPS activists, we can find a statement about the numerous obligations that lie on the shoulders of women, while the lack of existing civil rights and more. The authors originating from the National Independence Party also highlighted the current situation of solving women's problems, affecting the ignorance of men deciding the fate of the entire nation. However, one can notice a significant difference between the previously described appeal of PPS activists and the second one from the National Independence Party. The second appeal, in its content was not so urgent, its authors in a gentler, more subtle way tried to make women aware of the positive sides of gaining political and public awareness. So, they exchanged advantages:

“(…), having political rights, the woman will become acquainted with the entire complex of our national and social life, expand her worldview, raise her civic dignity, stop being passive, indecisive and cowardly. By obtaining rights to the Sejm and local government, Polish women become true citizens of their beloved homeland” (The Central Archives of Historical Records, the Ostrowski and Potocki Archives of Maluszyn..., 1919, Party of National Independence, p. 2).

The authors familiarized readers with previous years in which women applied for civil rights. These efforts were directed to the first Council of State, to the Regency Council, to the ministerial minister Kucharzewski and the ministerial minister Świeżyński. Then, in the appeal, allegations were made about the lack of earlier

possibility for women to influence the fate of the nation. Activists also warned of the National Democracy, whose intentions they considered insincere. They then call on women to vote for the United Republican Election Committee on list 1:

“So, in her own interest and in the interest of the good of the future and power of the nation, a woman should go along with Polish democracy, and the sincerest representatives are the candidates of the UNITED REPUBLICAN ELECTION COMMITTEE, LISTING NO.1” (The Central Archives of Historical Records, the Ostrowski and Potocki Archives of Maluszyn..., 1919, Party of National Independence, p. 2).

The authors once again emphasized the importance of elections to the Legislative Sejm and the need for women to vote. The second part of the appeal of the National Independence Party showed the possibility of female representatives entering the Legislative Sejm. Then it was pointed out the responsibility that will rest on women who get to the Sejm – and this is primarily a fight for equal rights in matters of work, earnings, positions (Zackiewicz, 2018, p. 204). The authors also tackled the problem of marriage and its inseparability, commenting that it disturbs a certain freedom of a man who remains unhappy. To protect family and marriage rights, the authors of the brochure saw women who would enter the Legislative Sejm and become MPs. Like the activists of PPS, they raise the matter of motherhood and the situation of pregnant women, which should be changed without delay:

“The reborn Polish State, after so many years of war disasters and terrifying mortality, must create laws that would guarantee the nation's development, strength and due population growth. (...) To this end, a special law on maternity insurance and a directly related right to child protection must be created” (The Central Archives of Historical Records, the Ostrowski and Potocki Archives of Maluszyn..., 1919, Party of National Independence, p. 3).

In the last part of their appeal, the authors drew attention to social problems, which were: prostitution, alcoholism, and smoking. Finally, they pay attention to the attribute of women, which is a more altruistic and emotional attitude – which will undoubtedly be a new element in political life. This leads to greater reflection, discussion of many decisions made by men – among the issues rejected by a woman include, inter alia, war or other bloody conflicts.

Conclusions

Both appeals set out a number of policy issues and the women involved directly and indirectly. Political parties tried to convince by all means women to vote for their party or party. This is not surprising, due to the fact that women being half the nation, received the rights and had a significant impact on the course of the election. Agitations led by different parties have outdone each other in portraying the role of women in elections. Not only on the part of women voters, but also women candidates who are to remain the representation of women in the Legislative Sejm. Women,

however, faced a difficult choice, surrounded by promises from all sides. Having no experience in political life, they had to decide what they want for their homeland and whom they could trust. It was not an easy task, even because of the fact that women have been removed from politics so far, which led to their ignorance and lack of awareness. It should be noted, however, that both appeals, despite the environments in which they were issued, are in fact similar to each other and raise the same issues. This shows us a picture of the life of the rebirthing the Second Polish Republic and the issues that were to be changed. The problem of choosing the appropriate authorities representing the voice of the nation was and is still a difficult and complicated issue, which is why it is necessary to understand and appreciate the behavior of women who suddenly gained a voice in the political life of the Second Polish Republic.

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Photo 1. Elections to the Sejm and the Feminine Case – Central Election Office P. P. S. Feminine Department of the Polish Socialist Party, Source: Central Archives of Historical Records, Ostrowski and Potocki Archives from Maluszyn, prints on the elections to the legislative parliament (posters, appeals, leaflets), 1919.

POLEKA PARTJA SOCJALISTYCZNA.

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P. P. S. № 2. *Legja wyborcza do I go sejmu* **P. P. S. № 2.**

Do Kobiet!

Towarzyszki! Obywatelki!

Po latach przemocy obec nadeszła dla ludu polskiego chwila wyzwolenia i otosam, własna wola zbiorowa stanowiąc ma o tem, jak się dalej rządzić i jakie ma być w Polsce prawo.

Zbliżają się wybory do Sejmu ustawodawczego, który ma określić, ustanowić i zatwierdzić ten nowy ład w Polsce, nowe prawa naszego życia społecznego.

Kobiety! W jednym szerezu z mężczyznami stańcie do współpracy w tem wielkim dziele! Rząd ludowy udzieli wszystkim obywatelkom kraju równego prawa głosowania i wybieralności. Równy głos posiada dziś najuboższa wyrobienica i parobek wiejski, jak magnat i fabrykant!

Kobiety! Strzeżcie tego skarbku obywatelskiej równości i pamiętajcie, że skorzystanie z przysługującego nam prawa jest naszym obowiązkiem. Nikomu nie wolno uchylać się od udziału w wyborach do Sejmu ustawodawczego. Nikomu nie wolno powiadzić sobie: obajdzia się tam bez mojego głosu! Ani ledne sumienie w Polsce spać nie powinno. Żadnym rekiem bezczynnie złożonym spojzywać nie wolno w tej dobie, kiedy przyszłość ludu polskiego się rozstrzyga!

Towarzyszki! Obywatelki! Jaka państwo zbudujemy, w takim żyć będą nasze dzieci!

Dzieci! Dzieci nasze marzą z głodu. Nadsza, ciemnota milionowych rzesz ludu robotniczego, wyniszczenie, tubercuza ofiar wojny i pałeczki kapitala co z wyszku tej podry wyrosł — oto co nam zostawił w dziedzictwie stary porządek!

Kobiety! Jest dużo do postanowienia i zmiany na lepsze!

Jeżeli chcecie, by nigdy już na świecie nie rozpętała się nowa wojna,

by każdy człowiek przeciętny miał zapewnione dostateczne środki utrzymania i równe prawo udziału w rządach kraju,

by nie było "klas" i "warstw" wyzysku państwa, kamienicy, by wszyscy równo

mieli prawa do ciepłych, jasnych mieszkań by dzieci nasze miały zapewnioną naukę i wychowanie w szkołach powszechnych dostateczne odżywianie, pomoc lekarzów, by roali w zdrowiu i swobodzie,

by każda matka miała zapewnioną pomoc państwowa na okres macierzyństwa by radośnie spełniać mogła to szczerne powołanie włożone na nią przez naturę;

jeżeli chcecie, by wszelkie prawo w Polsce dyktowała praca, nie zaś posiadanie bogactw:

Wybierajcie do Sejmu Ustawodawczego tych, którzy od dziesiątków lat walczą o wyzwolenie ludu pracującego od wszelkiej przemocy i wyzysku, którzy w mozolnym, pełnym ofiar trudzie dążyli zawsze do tego, by w Polsce, a której niepodległość walczyli, dobrze było wszystkim, nie tylko młodości urzędowej.

Wybierajcie socjalistów umieszczonych na liście Polskiej Partji Socjalistycznej! Lista № 2.

Kobiety! Są nas w Polsce miliony, stanowimy większą część jej ludności, w naszych rękach, w naszych sumieniach spoczywa los naszej przyszłości!

Towarzyszki! Obywatelki! Zbudujcie się wszystkie, niech żadna nie poniesie swego obywatelskiego obowiązku, nie zmarnotrawicie głosu otrzymanego, nie dajcie posłucha nieproszonym opiekunom, którzy tydzień sieci zarabiają na Wasze dusze, by zohydzić w oczach Waszych wielki ruch ludowy, a przystępić do urny wyborczej z głosem na nasłów

Polskiej Partji Socjalistycznej! Lista № 2.

Za naszą wolą niech zginie przemoc, wyzysk i ciemnota.

Za naszą wolą niech się stanie wolna Polska przetrzeźwiona lud!

Głosujcie wszystkie na listę № 2.

Wdziął Kobietcy
 Polskiej Partji Socjalistycznej.

Photo 2. Appeal to women – Polish Socialist Party, Source: Central Archives of Historical Records, Ostrowski and Potocki Archives from Maluszyn, prints on elections to the legislative parliament (posters, appeals, leaflets), 1919.

Warszawa 1919
Sejm Ustawodawczy
85

Polska Partja Socjalistyczna.

Matki-Obywatelki!

Jeśli Wam droga jest przyszłość Waszych dzieci:
jeśli chcecie, aby dzieci Wasze otrzymały bezpłatne wykształcenie;
jeśli chcecie, aby dzieci Wasze nie marły z głodu;
jeśli chcecie, aby dzieci Wasze były odziane i obute;
jeśli chcecie, aby dzieci Wasze wyrastały na uczciwych i dzielnych obywateli swojego kraju,
przybywajcie tłumnie w dniu *25* Stycznia r. b. o godz. 5 po poł na

WIEC MATEK

który odbędzie się w lokalu.....

przy ulicy *Bożowa* No *4*

Na wiecu tym omówione będą postulaty, jakie mają być wystawione w Sejmie Ustawodawczym i poruszona sprawa, komu należy powierzyć obronę tych postulatów.

Komitet Wyborczy
Polskiej Partji Socjalistycznej
Okręgu Warszawskiego.

Warszawa, dn. 17/I—1919 r.

Photo 3. Mothers' meeting – Polish Socialist Party, Source: Central Archives of Historical Records, Ostrowski and Potocki Archives from Maluszyn, prints on the elections to the legislative parliament (posters, appeals, leaflets), 1919.

Photo 4. Task of a woman in the Legislative Sejm – Party of National Independence, Source: Central Archives of Historical Records, Ostrowski and Potocki Archives of Maluszyn, prints on the elections to the legislative parliament (posters, appeals, leaflets), 1919.

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The Role of a Woman Voting in the 1919 Legislative Sejm Elections

Pic. 5 and 6. Polish women! – National Election Organization of Polish Women, Source: Central Archives of Historical Records, Ostrowski and Potocki Archives from Maluszyn, prints on elections to the legislative parliament (posters, appeals, leaflets), 1919.

Pic. 7 and 8. Polish Women – National Election Organization of Polish Women, Source: Central Archives of Historical Records, Ostrowski and Potocki Archives from Maluszyn, prints on the elections to the legislative parliament (posters, appeals, leaflets), 1919.